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Effect of drama method of teaching chemistry on the interest of students in secondary schools in Rivers State

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Abstract

Chemistry is a foundational science that supports human advancement in areas such as health, energy, and technology. Despite its importance, students often perceive chemistry as abstract and difficult, resulting in low interest and poor academic performance. Interest, a motivational factor that drives learning and persistence, can be cultivated through instructional strategies. This study investigates the effect of using the drama method to teach the concept of atoms and ions on the interest levels of chemistry students in the Rivers-East Senatorial District of Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examines differences in students' mean interest scores between those taught with the drama method and those taught using traditional lecture methods, as well as gender-based differences among students exposed to the drama method. Guided by two research questions and two hypotheses tested at the 0.05 significance level, the study applies interest theory and the four-phase model of interest development to assess the impact of engaging, context-rich instruction. Findings show how creative teaching strategies like drama foster greater student interest, enhance academic motivation, and improve chemistry learning outcomes across gender.

Keywords: Drama; Teaching; Chemistry; Interest; Secondary Schools

1. Introduction

Chemistry is an incredibly fascinating field of study. Because it is so fundamental to our world, chemistry plays a role in everyone's lives and touches almost every aspect of our existence in some way. Chemistry is essential for meeting our basic needs of food, clothing, shelter, health, energy, and clean air, water and soil. Chemical technologies enrich our quality of life in numerous ways by providing new solutions to problems in health, materials, and energy usage. Thus, studying chemistry is useful in preparing us for the real world (Research Interest of the Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry (UW-La Crosse, 2023).

Chemistry is a core subject for various disciplines, including pharmacology, physiology, chemical industries and environment. The uniqueness of chemistry makes it occupy a pride of place in the technological and scientific progress of any nation. Unfortunately, chemistry is widely perceived as non-concrete and challenging by both students and educators. Also, evidence from reports of chief examiners of West African Examinations Council (WAEC), and National Examinations Council (NECO), shows that students' interest in chemistry and science related subjects generally are not encouraging (WAEC, 2020).

Chemistry as a school subject has been a source of fright to most science students. This fright is caused by anxiety. Anxiety is one of the major predictors of academic performance. Students with anxiety disorder display a passive attitude in their studies such as lack of interest in learning (Taber, 2013, Daigety and Coll, 2006).

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1.1. Concept of Interest in Learning

Interest is a cognitive and affective motivational variable that is malleable and can be cultivated at any age. It refers to a person's psychological state during engagement with some content, as well as the motivation to seek information and reengage with that content over time (Renninger and Hidi, 2020). Interest development benefits the quality of individuals' work with tasks, activities, and assignments. Interest enables people to be more conscientious, able to persist, and ready to work with negative feedback; when students exhibit these characteristics, this makes teaching rewarding. Instruction and curricular materials (texts, problems) can be anchored in questions that students in the class generate or those that researchers have identified as questions shared by students at that age (Hagay and Baram-Tsabari, 2011).

The effect of interest on decision making also has implications for policies, such as whether course work should be required (e.g., mathematics, physics). Given that interest is needed to make an informed choice, students with little to no background should not be asked to make a choice about courses to take. Were the requirements to take such courses coupled with instructional practices specifically designed to trigger and develop interest, students' subsequent possibilities (e.g., advanced course work, jobs in a wide range of fields) would open up. (Egolum, Okonkwo, Nkiru and Samuel, 2022).

Psychological interest, according to Ahuja (2001), is a person's propensity for behavior toward a certain thing or a group of things they engage in. He added that enthusiasm is a very powerful motivator and no one attacks a task energetically unless he has interest in it. Interest develops working skills more effectively because to be interested in something is to be absorbed and to be carried away by it. The function of interest is to engage learners in activities, which they continuously and consistently carry out. To secure the learners' interest, therefore, means to attach some features of seductiveness to the activities.

A learning situation should involve the learner if he is to gain significantly from it. According to Ekeke (1987), unless a learning situation is arranged in a way that would arouse and maintain students' interest they will not learn well or work consistently. Interest is an individual mental schema related to the interesting activity or object based on positive emotional experience and individual value system (Köller et al., 2001). Other beliefs claimed that individual and situational interest will increase perseverance in completing the task, paying attention, brainstorming, and optimizing effort (Hidi and Renninger, 2006). Therefore, it encourages the improvement of academic success. Concerning academic interest, Farruggia et al. (2016), inferred that academic success requires a strong academic mindset. Students who possess high academic interests will expand continually their learning skills on accounting. This is important as the presence of negative perception is known to be an uninteresting course of accounting (Jackling, 2002; Kögler and Göllner, 2018), thus, affect academic performance. Academic interest is also strongly related to self-efficacy, therefore, affect significantly the learning outcomes and academic performance (Fallan and Opstad, 2014).

Interest is both a mental state that is defined by increased attention, effort, and emotion felt at a certain time (situational interest) and a long-term propensity back return to a specific item or topic over time (individual interest), (Hidi and Renninger, 2006). Interest is a powerful motivational process that energizes learning, guides academic and career trajectories, and is essential to academic success. Interest is both a psychological state of attention and affect towards a particular object or topic, and an enduring predisposition to reengage over time. Integrating these two definitions, the four-phase model of interest development guides interventions that promote and capitalize on existing interests. Four interest-enhancing interventions seem useful: attention-getting settings, context evoking prior individual interest, problem-based learning, and enhancing utility value (Hidi and Renninger, 2006).

Promoting interest can contribute to a more engaged, motivated, learning experience for students (Harackiewicz, Smith, and Priniski, 2016). Interest is both a mental state that is defined by increased attention, effort, and emotion felt at a certain time (situational interest) and a long-term propensity back return to a specific item or topic over time (individual interest), (Hidi and Renninger, 2006). Interest is a powerful motivational process that energizes learning, guides academic and career trajectories, and is essential to academic success. Interest is both a psychological state of attention and affect towards a particular object or topic, and an enduring predisposition to reengage over time. Integrating these two definitions, the four-phase model of interest development guides interventions that promote and capitalize on existing interests. Four interest-enhancing interventions seem useful: attention-getting settings, context evoking prior individual interest, problem-based learning, and enhancing utility value. Promoting interest can contribute to a more engaged, motivated, learning experience for students (Harackiewicz, Smith, and Priniski, 2016).

Schiefele, (2011) stated that recent research related to the concept of interest is reviewed. It is argued that current constructs of motivation fail to include crucial aspects of the meaning of interest emphasized by classical American and

German educational theorists. In contrast with many contemporary concepts (e.g., intrinsic learning orientation), interest is defined as a content-specific motivational characteristic composed of intrinsic feeling-related and value-related valences. Results from a number of studies are presented that indicate the importance of interest for the depth of text comprehension, the use of learning strategies, and the quality of the emotional experience while learning (Schiefele, 2011).

Psychologists have always been interested in interest, and so modern research on interest can be found in nearly every area of the field: Researchers studying emotions, cognition, development, education, aesthetics, personality, motivation and vocations have developed intriguing ideas about what interest is and how it works. Exploring the psychology of interest presents an integrated picture of how interest has been studied in all the wide-ranging area of psychology (Krapp, 2002). Using modern theories of psychology and emotions as an integrative framework, Paul Silva (2006), examines the nature of interest, what makes things interesting, the role of interest in personality, and development of people's idiosyncratic interest, hobbies and vocations. His examination reveals deep similarities between seemingly different fields of psychology and illustrates the profound importance of interest, curiosity and intrinsic motivation for understanding why people do what they do (Silva, 2006).

Also, Najami, Hugerat, Khalil, and Hofstein, stated the effectiveness of teaching science by Drama, explored the impact of drama on students' achievement and motivation in learning chemistry the researchers found that students who learned through drama showed significant improvement in their understanding and motivation compared to those who learned through traditional methods.

Drama involves doing something as it is real. Therefore, it provides a presentation and interpretation of a physical or mental activity and is a way to transform students' mental and physical potentials into creative acts (Durusel, 2007). Drama is an adaptation, recreation and reflection of reality on stage. Drama is a performance-based literary genre, which is why Yanni (cited in Dukore, 2020) calls it "staged art." because characters are given roles and act those roles). Studying science through drama can help students view science as a humane social experience that involves and motivates them to develop an understanding of the world which is rooted in scientific and humanistic traditions. This in turn will draw them closer to science and increase their interest to study it (Stinner, 1995, Peleg and Baram-Tsabari, 2011). Drama has also been used in science education to stimulate development of inquiry-skills, as well as to assess how children progress in their knowledge and thinking about science. Bailey (Bailey, 1993) maintains that drama is capable of promoting students' understanding and that it enhances their learning by exploiting group work. It also strengthens students' positive self-image, because the basic concepts of drama serve to express the ego; hence, students can use it to bring their own personal experiences into the action is performed on stage, it is a literary genre that is intended for the theater.

This study is therefore designed to investigate the effect of Drama on the Interest of chemistry students in secondary schools in Rivers-East Senatorial District.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to find out the effect of using drama method to teach atoms and ions, on the interest of chemistry students in Rivers-East Senatorial district of Rivers State.

Specifically, the study intends to

- Determine the difference in the mean interest of chemistry students when taught atoms and ions with drama and those taught using lecture methods.
- Determine the difference in the mean interest of male and female chemistry students when taught atoms and ions using drama.

Research Questions

- What is the difference in the mean interest of chemistry students when taught atoms and ions with drama and those taught using lecture method?
- What is the difference in the mean interest of male and female chemistry students when taught atoms and ions using drama?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- There is no significant difference in the mean interest of chemistry students when taught atoms and ions with drama method and those taught same concept using lecture method.
- There is no significant difference in the mean interest of male and female chemistry students when taught atoms and ions using drama method.

2. Methodology

Quas experimental research design as well survey design were used. The area covered by the study are all the eight Local Government Areas in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State, which include; Obio/Akpo, Port-Harcourt, Emohua, Okirika, Ogu/Bolo, Etche, Omuma, Ikwerre

The population for the study is all the SS1- SS3 in the 120 schools in that Senatorial district. The sample size for this study is 335 SS1 chemistry students. Intact classes with multistage sampling was used for this research

Table 1 Sample Distribution Table

S/N	School	SS1 A Experimental Class		SS1B Control class		Total
		M	F	M	F	
1	Community Sec. School, Nkpolu-Oruworukwo, PH.	20	25	22	28	95
2	Community Secondary School, Aluu, Ikwerre L.G. A	24	21	20	17	82
3	Army Day Secondary School, Bori-Camp (Obio/Akpo)	16	20	15	22	73
4	Community Sec. school, Egwi, Etche	18	25	20	22	85
	Grand Total	78	91	77	89	335

The research instrument used for this research was a structured questionnaire on students' interest in chemistry, adopted from the electronic supplementary material for chemistry education and practice, from the Royal Society of chemistry journal, adopted and used for this purpose.

2.1. Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistical tool of Mean and Standard Deviation was used to answer the researcher's questions, while Mann Whitney test

Students interest in chemistry questionnaire (SICQ), consists of 20 items on a (4) point Likert-scale of Strongly Agree, (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (DA), and a nominal value of 4, 3, 2 and 1 are attached to it. Since the total value is 10, a score of 5.0 is considered to agree, while any score below 5.0 is said to disagree

3. Results

3.1. Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean interest of chemistry students when taught atoms and ions with drama and those taught using lecture method?

Table 2 Mean Interest in Chemistry for Control and Experimental Groups

S/N	Students Interest in Chemistry Based on Method	Control (n = 166)			Experimental (n = 169)		
		\bar{x}	SD	RMK	\bar{x}	SD	RMK
1	I am very interested in chemistry	2.25	0.92	D	3.06	0.79	A
2	You love to watch tv programs on chemistry	2.23	0.85	D	3.05	0.85	A
3	You love to borrow or buy books and other materials on chemistry	2.19	0.98	D	2.88	0.97	A
4	Chemistry is your favorite subject, because I hardly forget concepts if I have learnt it	2.23	0.94	D	2.80	0.94	A
5	You find chemistry to be quite interesting	2.22	0.93	D	2.93	0.83	A
6	You feel very excited when I am to learn chemistry	2.17	0.91	D	3.04	0.84	A
7	You always enjoy chemistry lesson discussions	2.20	0.83	D	3.15	0.83	A
8	You like to study chemistry on my own	2.05	0.82	D	3.15	0.80	A
9	You would like to do better in chemistry	2.34	0.99	D	3.02	0.94	A
10	You have been very interested in chemistry since I was young	2.31	0.94	D	3.14	0.83	A
11	You always look forward to having chemistry lessons because they are very enjoyable to me.	2.25	0.88	D	3.04	0.90	A
12	You are considering pursuing a career in chemistry later in my life	2.37	0.88	D	2.95	0.90	A
13	Outside of school, you read a lot of chemistry related books	2.36	0.91	D	2.91	0.87	A
14	You watch a lot of chemistry related tv programs, because you love them	2.26	0.88	D	3.19	0.82	A
15	When you are reading or watching something about chemistry on tv, I am always focused.	2.37	0.96	D	2.95	0.91	A
16	You like to explain chemistry concepts to fellow students.	2.45	0.91	D	2.79	1.00	A
17	You like to work on chemistry projects because it helps me to understand what is happening around me better.	2.35	0.98	D	2.98	0.90	A
18	You love to do chemistry classwork and homework always because they give me the opportunity to understand more.	2.30	0.92	D	2.86	0.97	A
19	You always love it when I do micro-teaching in chemistry lessons because my understanding becomes more reliable when I teach others.	2.31	0.96	D	2.98	0.88	A
20	you love to listen to radio programs on chemistry because it helps me remember concepts that my teacher has taught me	2.18	0.92	D	2.89	0.95	A
	Grand Mean	2.27		D	2.99		A

Source: Field Work, SPSS Output (2024)

The result shows students' interest in chemistry. As shown, the result suggests that students of the experimental group had higher level of interest than the students of the control group. This is evident by mean responses being less than 2.50 for all the items of the control group and mean response being higher than 2.50 for all the items in the experimental group. Furthermore, grand mean value of 2.27 for the control group and grand mean value of 2.99 for the experimental group confirm that students in the experimental group had higher level of interest in atoms and ions than their counterparts in the control group.

3.2. Research Question 2

What is the difference in the mean interest of male and female chemistry students when taught atoms and ions using drama?

Table 3 Table for Mean Interest in Chemistry for Males and Females Taught with Drama

S/N	Students Interest in Chemistry Based on Gender	Boys (n = 78)			Girls (n = 91)		
		M	SD	RMK	M	SD	RMK
1	You are very interested in chemistry	3.09	0.71	A	3.03	0.86	A
2	You love to watch tv programs on chemistry	3.12	0.82	A	2.99	0.88	A
3	You love to borrow or buy books and other materials on chemistry	3.23	0.80	A	2.57	1.00	A
4	Chemistry is my favorite subject, because I hardly forget concepts if I have learnt it	2.81	1.01	A	2.79	0.89	A
5	You find chemistry to be quite interesting	2.95	0.82	A	2.91	0.84	A
6	You feel very excited when I am to learn chemistry	3.22	0.73	A	2.88	0.89	A
7	You always enjoy chemistry lesson discussions	3.14	0.85	A	3.15	0.82	A
8	You like to study chemistry on my own	3.13	0.81	A	3.18	0.80	A
9	You would like to do better in chemistry	2.85	0.99	A	3.16	0.86	A
10	You have been very interested in chemistry since I was young	3.24	0.74	A	3.04	0.89	A
11	You always look forward to having chemistry lessons because they are very enjoyable for me	3.21	0.89	A	2.90	0.88	A
12	You are considering pursuing a career in chemistry later in my life	2.77	0.94	A	3.10	0.84	A
13	Outside of school, I read a lot of chemistry related books	2.90	0.89	A	2.92	0.86	A
14	You watch a lot of chemistry related tv programs, because I love them	3.31	0.74	A	3.09	0.86	A
15	When You are reading or watching something about chemistry on tv, I am always focused	3.05	0.80	A	2.86	0.98	A
16	You like to explain chemistry concepts to fellow students	2.88	0.88	A	2.71	1.09	A
17	You like to work on chemistry projects because it helps me to understand what is happening around me better	3.27	0.73	A	2.74	0.96	A
18	You love to do chemistry classwork and homework always because they give me the opportunity to understand more	3.17	0.80	A	2.59	1.03	A
19	You always love it when You do micro-teaching in chemistry lessons because my understanding becomes more reliable when I teach others	3.17	0.81	A	2.82	0.91	A
20	You love to listen to radio programs on chemistry because it helps me to remember concepts that my teacher has taught me.	3.14	0.82	A	2.68	1.00	A
	Grand Mean	3.08		A	2.91		A

Source: Field Work, SPSS Output (2024)

The result shows interest in atoms and ions between boys and girls. As shown, the result suggests that boys had slightly higher level of interest than the girls. This is evident by grand mean value of 3.08 for the boys and 2.91 for the girls.

3.2.1. Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the interest of chemistry students when taught atoms and ions with drama and those taught using lecture method.

Table 4 Mean Ranks for Interest in Chemistry between Experimental and Control Groups

Method	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Control	166	122.35	20310
Experimental	169	212.84	35970
Total	335		

Source: Field Work, (2025)

The Table above, shows the result for the mean ranks for the control and experimental groups. As shown, the experimental group had the higher mean rank (212.84) against the control group with mean rank of 122.35. This is an indication that the experimental group exposed to instruction in Chemistry through drama had higher level of interest in Chemistry than their counterparts exposed to instruction in Chemistry through lecture method.

Table 5 Mann Whitney Test for Interest in Chemistry between Experimental and Control Groups

Test	Interest
Mann-Whitney U	6449.000
Wilcoxon W	20310.000
Z	-9.565
p-value (2-tailed)	0.000

a. Grouping Variable: Method; Source: Field Work, (2025)

From result above, it can be deduced that interest level among the experimental group was statistically significantly higher than the control group ($U = 6449, p = .000$). This implies that there was a significant difference in the interest of students in chemistry when taught with drama or with lecture method.

3.2.2. Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean interest of male and female chemistry students when taught atoms and ions using drama.

Table 6 Mean Ranks for Interest in Chemistry between males and females taught with Drama

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Boys	78	94.29	7354.50
Girls	91	77.04	7010.50
Total	169		

Source: Field Work, (2025)

The result in the above table, shows the result for the mean ranks for the males and females. As shown, the males had the higher mean rank (94.29) against the females with mean rank of 77.04. This is an indication that the males had higher level of interest in Chemistry than females.

Table 7 Mann Whitney Test for Interest in Chemistry between males and females taught with Drama

Test	Interest
Mann-Whitney U	2824.500
Wilcoxon W	7010.500
Z	-2.846
P-value (2-tailed)	0.004

a. Grouping Variable: Gender; Source: Field Work, (2025)

From result above, it can be deduced that interest level among the males was statistically significantly higher than the females ($U = 2824.5, p = .000$). This implies that there was a significant difference in the mean interest of male and female chemistry students when taught atoms and ions using drama.

3.3. Summary of Major Findings

Students exposed to instruction in Chemistry using drama teaching method had a significant higher level of interest than the students exposed to instruction in Chemistry using the lecture teaching method.

Male students exposed to instruction in Chemistry through drama had a significant higher level of interest in Chemistry than girls.

3.4. Difference in the mean interest of chemistry students when taught atoms and ions with drama and those taught using lecture method

The results revealed that students taught using the drama method had a significantly higher level of interest in learning about atoms and ions compared to those taught through the lecture method. This was evident by the mean responses for the experimental group consistently exceeding 2.50 across all the items, while the control group had mean responses below 2.50. The grand mean values further emphasized this difference, with the experimental group achieving a grand mean of 2.99, compared to the control group's 2.27. This suggests that the students in the experimental group found the drama-based instructional approach more engaging and stimulating.

The increased interest among the experimental group could be attributed to the interactive and participatory nature of the drama teaching method. Drama as a pedagogical tool provides students with an opportunity to actively engage with the content through role-play, visualization, and collaboration. These elements foster greater curiosity, creativity, and emotional involvement, making the learning process more enjoyable and meaningful for students. In contrast, the lecture method, which is often more passive, may not stimulate the same level of interest or excitement in students. The confirmation from the hypothesis also demonstrates a significant difference in students' interest between the two groups, further validates these findings. The statistical significance highlights that the difference in interest levels was not due to chance but rather a direct result of the instructional method used. The drama method's ability to capture and maintain students' attention, likely through its dynamic and interactive nature, played a key role in enhancing students' interest in the subject matter.

These findings are consistent with educational research, which suggests that student engagement and interest are critical to improving learning outcomes. When students are more interested in a subject, they are more likely to be motivated, participate actively, and invest more effort in understanding the content. In this case, the drama teaching method appears to have effectively harnessed these factors, leading to a higher level of interest and potentially contributing to the better academic performance observed in the experimental group.

Generally, the results implies that the use of drama significantly increased students' interest in learning atoms and ions compared to the lecture method. This higher interest level likely created a more conducive learning environment, reinforcing the value of innovative and interactive teaching strategies in improving student engagement and overall learning experiences. The result corroborates that of Okpala and Okigbo (2021) who found that students exposed to instruction in electrolysis through role play had significant higher interest score than students exposed to same instruction through conventional teaching method. This result also agrees with Atabo and Abuh (2010) when they assert that, an advantage (which as well becomes an aim) of the drama and theatre method is that interest is enhanced and concepts are remembered longer as a result of participation. As a result, they performed better in the test.

Furthermore, the result agrees with the result by Obijiofor (2020) who found that students exposed to instruction through role play method had higher level of interest in English Language than students exposed to instruction through the conventional teaching method. Also, Veder-Weiss (2013), after investigating the drop in motivation to study science and the effect of various elements in the educational Environment stated that drama, as a teaching method, was effective in motivating students towards learning the subject and towards the sciences in general. The career interest and science related attitudes of science majors were found to have significant improvement; some students' perception toward science careers and science have changed after the activity. Some students commented that creative drama had developed their courage, social skills, teamwork, creativity, self-reflection, presentation skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. (Ong et al., 2018).

3.5. Difference in the mean interest of male and female chemistry students when taught atoms and ions using drama

This result of research question two shows that there was a slight difference in the level of interest in atoms and ions between male and female students, with boys showing a marginally higher level of interest than girls. The grand mean value of 3.08 for the boys compared to 2.91 for the girls suggests that while both groups expressed interest in the subject matter when taught using the drama method, the boys exhibited a slightly greater enthusiasm. This small difference, though seemingly minimal, reflects a trend where boys were somewhat more engaged or interested in the topic than their female counterparts. However, the test of hypothesis five showed that this difference in interest between male and female students was statistically significant. This finding suggests that gender played a role in influencing students' level of interest when the drama method was used to teach atoms and ions. The statistical significance of this difference implies that boys and girls responded differently to the drama-based teaching approach in terms of their interest, with boys showing a more favorable reaction.

The significant difference in interest levels may be attributed to various factors, such as learning preferences, engagement with the teaching method, or prior experiences with the subject matter. Boys might have found the drama method more engaging, possibly due to the active and participatory nature of the teaching style, which could align with their learning preferences. On the other hand, while girls also demonstrated high interest, the slightly lower mean score suggests they may have responded differently to certain aspects of the teaching method.

The result showed that while boys had higher interest, both genders still exhibited mean scores above 2.50, indicating a generally positive reception of the drama method across both groups. The drama teaching approach appears to have successfully engaged both boys and girls, even though the level of engagement was slightly higher for the boys. It can therefore be deduced that the drama teaching method was effective in generating interest in atoms and ions for both male and female students, but with boys demonstrating a significantly higher level of interest. This finding highlights the importance of considering gender differences in the teaching and learning process, as different teaching methods may suit differently with male and female students. Understanding these dynamics can help educators tailor their instructional strategies to ensure both boys and girls are equally engaged and motivated to learn. The result agrees with the result by Okpala and Okigbo (2021) who also found male students had higher mean interest score than their female counterparts, exposed to instruction in electrolysis through role play teaching method. In their study, Kasbary and Novák (2024) found that drama stimulated students, as they were more enthusiastic about exploring, examining and learning, socializing with their groupmates. It also aided students' confidence to perform well in their academic activities. Furthermore, the result agrees with the result by Obijiofor (2020) who found that students exposed to instruction through role play method had higher academic achievement than students exposed to instruction through the conventional teaching method in English Language.

Implications of the Study

This study implies that, for students' interest in chemistry to be elevated, drama method of teaching must be deployed in explaining the concepts in chemistry.

Recommendations

Education policy makers should see it as a matter of urgency to make drama a compulsory course for would be teachers in higher education at all level. Drama activities take time; therefore, lesson time should be adjusted by the time table planners to take care of the periods for each lesson.

4. Conclusion

The study examined the effect of drama teaching method on students' interest in chemistry. Findings from the study show that Students exposed to instruction in Chemistry using drama teaching method had a significant higher level of interest than the students exposed to instruction in Chemistry using the lecture teaching method and that male students exposed to instruction in Chemistry through drama had a significantly higher level of interest in Chemistry than girls. We therefore conclude that use of Drama in teaching Chemistry is effective in improving students' interest and motivation in the subject, and could enhance students' performance.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict-of-interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Ahuja, G. C. (2001). Handbook for group test of Intelligence (13 to 17 + years). Agra: National Psychological Cooperation.
- [2] Bailey, R. (1993, 8(1)). Dramatic world: A Critical Study of Drama in Education. Journal of Drama and Theatre Education, 15-21.
- [3] Durusel, G. (2007). İlkogretim Okullari igin uygulamali drama. Istanbul: Yuva Yayinlari.
- [4] Fallan, L. and Opstad, L. (2014). Beyond Gender Performance in Accounting: Does Personality Matter? Accounting Education journal, 343-461.
- [5] Farrugia, S. P., Han, C., Watson, L., Moss, T. P and Bottoms, B. L. (2016). Noncognitive factors and College students' Success. Journal of College Students' Retention: Research, Theory and Practice, 308-327.
- [6] Hagay, G., and Baram-Tsabari, A. (2011). A Shadow curriculum, Incorporating Students; into the formal biology curriculum. Research in Science Education, 611-634.
- [7] Harackiewicz, M. J., Smith, L. J., and Priniski, J. S. (July, 7, 2016). Interest Matters: The Importance of Promoting Interest in Education. SAGE journals.
- [8] Hidi, S. and Renninger, K. A. (2006). The four phase Model of Interest Development. Educational Psychologist, 111-127.
- [9] Koller, O., Baumert, J and Schnabel, K., (2001). Does Interest Matter? The Relationship between Academic Interest and Achievement in Mathematics in Education. Journal For Research in Mathematics Education, 448-478.
- [10] Jackling, B. (2002). Are Negative Perceptions of the Accounting Profession Perpetuated by Introductory Accounting Course? An Australian study. Asian Review of Accounting, 62-80.
- [11] Kogler, K and Golliner, R. (2018). Control-Value Appraisals Predicting Students' boredom in Accounting Class: A Continuous state sampling approach. Empirical Research in Vocational Education and Training, 1-16.
- [12] Najah, S.B., and Salih, M.M. ((2021). Using drama-based instruction to improve tertiary students' retention of organic chemistry concepts. International Journal of Higher Education, 100-112.
- [13] Obijiofor, E. (2020). Effect of Role-Play Method on Primary School Pupils' Academic Achievement and Interest in English Studies in Anambra State. International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Research.
- [14] Okpala, U. V., and Okigbo, E. C. (2021). Effect of role play on secondary school students' achievement in chemistry. African Journal of Science, Technology and Mathematics Education, 53-60.

- [15] Ong, K.-J., Chou, Y.-C., Yang, D.-Y., and Lin, C.-C. (2018). Creative drama in science education: The effects on situational interest, career interest, and science-related attitudes of science majors and non-science majors. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 90–101.
- [16] Renninger, A. K, and Hiddi, S. E. (2020). *To Level the playing field, Develop Interest*. Sage
- [17] Schiefele, U. (2011). Interest, Learning and Motivation. *Educational Psychologist*, 299-323.
- [18] Silvia, J. P. (2006). *Exploring the Psychology of Interest*. Oxford university press.
- [19] tinner, A. (1995). Contextual Settings, Science Stories and Large Context Problems: Toward a More Humanistic Science Education. *Science Education*, 555-581
- [20] Vedder-Weiss, D. (2013). Adolescents' declining motivation to learn science: Inevitable or not? *Research in Science Teaching*, 199-216.